

Robotics in Agriculture

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

Agriculture is one of our most important industries and a big business in every country around the world. It provides food, feed and fuel necessary for our survival. With the global population expected to reach 9 billion by 2050, agricultural production must double to meet the demand. And because of limited arable land, productivity must increase 25% to help meet that goal. Thus a timely review of the progress to bring robotic automation to this industry is really necessary.

2. Aim

Robotics Automation in agricultural practices.

3. Material and methods

1. Automated guided vehicles (AGVs) for farming practices. Tractors do two things: provide guidance to the devices they are towing, and pulling power. Current tractors are huge and if they break down, the entire operation comes to a halt. Autonomous ground vehicles don't need operators and can operate around the clock. Thus tight operational windows can be achieved for seeding and other time-sensitive activities. Eg. - Current harvesting method in case of fruits and vegetables is only 60-65% efficient which can be scaled to 90% by means of automation.

2. Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) for Inspection and data collection. Unmanned aerial vehicles can be used to map the agriculturalable land, to observe and sense the crops as well as for spraying. The aerial perspective that drones offer reduces the need to go row by row to check crop health. Data from drone flights can be configured to show the number of crops, and some are even sophisticated enough to show a plant's height. Latest agriculture drones utilize infrared and thermal camera to capture field data such as chlorophyll levels. Advanced software can use images captured from drones to create 3D models to identify variables such as crop stress. Healthy plants can be distinguished and soil analysis is used for pinpointing the best areas to plant the next batch of seeds.

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4. Conclusions

UAVs and AGVs may be the farm workers of the future. On one end, drones have increased the spraying efficiency by 40-60%, the AGVs has increased the ploughing, seeding and harvesting efficiency by 30-50%.

5. Keywords

Robots in Agriculture, Smart harvesting and ploughing, automatic weeding, Driverless tractor/Sprayer, Drones in Agriculture

Author biography

Vivek Soni Vivek Soni has completed his graduation at the age of 22 years from Netaji Subhas Institute of Technology, University of Delhi, India. He started his robotics career at Grey orange robotics India where he worked on autonomous guided vehicles (AGVs) for warehouse automation. He is currently working as robotics engineer at Rapyuta robotics based in Japan.